

(43.82 %, or 44.05 %)-Limiting Highest Efficiencies, Obtained Respectively in $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ Crystalline CdS-Junction Solar Cells at $T=300$ K, Due to the Effects of Impurity Size, Temperature, Heavy Doping, and Photovoltaic Conversion

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Abstract:

In the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ crystalline ($X \equiv \text{CdS}$)-junction solar cells at 300K, due to the effects of impurity size, temperature, heavy doping, and photovoltaic conversion, we show that, with an increasing donor (acceptor)-radius $r_{d(a)}$, both the relative dielectric constant and photovoltaic conversion factor decrease, and the intrinsic band gap (IBG) increases, according to the increase in photovoltaic efficiency η , as observed in Tables 1-3. This is found to be in good accordance with an important result obtained by Shockley and Queisser (1961), stating that, for a fixed fraction of the total radiative recombination ($=1$) and for an increasing IBG [$0 < \text{IBG}(eV) \leq 1.1$], η increases and its maximum value is equal to 30 % at $\text{IBG}=1.1$ eV.

Further, for highest values of $r_{d(a)}$, the limiting highest efficiencies are found to be given in Tables 2 and 3, as: 43.82 %, and 44.05 %, obtained in such $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ crystalline CdS-junction solar cells at $T=300$ K, with a large value of IBG ($2.395 \text{ eV} \leq \text{IBG} \leq 2.462 \text{ eV}$, as seen in Table 1), and at the open circuit voltage $V_{oc} = 2.7$ V.

Furthermore, from the well-known Carnot-efficiency theorem, as given in Eq. (46), being obtained from the second principle of thermodynamics, and from the above results of limiting highest efficiencies, the corresponding highest hot reservoir temperatures, $T_H=534$ K, and 536 K, respectively. Thus, as noted above, both η_{max} and T_H increase with an increasing IBG, and at $T=300$ K $\equiv T_C$.

Keywords: donor (acceptor)-size effect; heavily doped emitter region; photovoltaic conversion factor; open circuit voltage; efficiency.

Introduction

In the present work, the limiting highest efficiencies, $\eta_{I(II)}$, due to the effects of impurity size, temperature, heavy doping, and photovoltaic conversion, will be investigated respectively in the heavily doped donor (acceptor)-CdS emitter-and-lightly doped acceptor (donor) CdS base-regions, HD[d(a)-CdS]ER-LD[a(d)-CdS]BR, of $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ junction solar cells; it is inspired from other works (Van Cong, 2022, 2016, 1999, 1995, 1991, 1975; Van Cong et al., 1997, 1996, 1993, 1992, 1984, 2022; Green,

1981; Green et al., 2022, 2010; He et al., 2022; Kate et al. 2013; Kittel, 1976; Levinshtein, 1999; Parola et al., 2019; Shockley & Queisser, 1961; Singh & Ravindra, 2012).

For each d(a)- CdS -crystal (Van Cong et al., 2022), one notes that: (i) due to the effect of donor (acceptor) d(a)- radius $r_{d(a)}$, with an increasing $r_{d(a)}$, the relative dielectric constant $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})$ decreases, while the band gap (BG), $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)})$, increases, as observed in Equations (1.1, 1.2), (ii) due the temperature (T)-effect, the intrinsic BG (IBG), $E_{gin(gip)}(T, r_{d(a)})$, decreases with increasing T, as given in Eq. (3), and (iii) due to the effect of heavy doping, with increasing d(a)-density, $N_{d(a)}$, while the Fermi energy increases, as given in Eq. (5), the BG is reduced by the BG narrowing, as observed in Equations (6) and (7). Therefore, as remarked in Section 5, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density, $J_{oI(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)})$, defined in Eq. (37), decreases with increasing IBG, or with increasing $r_{d(a)}$, given in the ER(BR).

Then, for each d(a)- CdS -crystal, the photovoltaic conversion effect converts the light, represented by the short circuit current density, defined in Eq. (41), $J_{scl(sclII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}; V_{oc})$, V_{oc} being the open circuit voltage, into the electricity, by $J_{oI(oII)}$.

Further, as observed in Tables 2 and 3, for a given V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), determined in Eq. (42), $n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}; V_{oc})$, decreases with increasing IBG, or with increasing $r_{d(a)}$, according to the increase in $J_{scl(sclII)}$, in the fill factor, $F_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}; V_{oc})$ and the efficiency $\eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}; V_{oc})$, defined respectively in Equations (43, 44). This remark is found to be in accordance with an important result obtained by Shockley and Queisser (1961), stating that for an increasing IBG, η increases.

Effects of Impurity Size, Temperature and Heavy Doping

First of all, in intrinsic CdS -crystals at temperature $T(=0\text{ K})$, and at $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)}$, the values of relative dielectric constant, $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}) = \varepsilon(r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)}) = \varepsilon_o$, effective average number of equivalent conduction (valence)-band edges, $g_{c(v)} = 1(1)$, relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands, $(m_{c(v)}/m_o)$, unperturbed intrinsic band gap, E_{go} , and effective ionization energies in absolute values, $E_{do(ao)} = \frac{13600 \times (m_{c(v)}/m_o)}{(\varepsilon_o)^2} \text{ meV}$, are given Table 1.

Impurity-Size Effect

In such d(a)- CdS systems at $T=0\text{ K}$, since $r_{d(a)}$, in tetrahedral covalent bonds, is usually either larger or smaller than $r_{do(ao)}$, a local mechanical strain (or deformation potential energy) is induced, according to a compression (or a dilation), for $r_{d(a)} > r_{do(ao)}$ (for $r_{d(a)} < r_{do(ao)}$), respectively, due to the d(a)-size effect, as that investigated (Van Cong et al., 2022). Further, in n(p)-type CdS crystals, the band gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)})$ and the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)})$ are expressed as:

$$\text{for } r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}, \text{ since } \varepsilon(r_{d(a)}) = \frac{\varepsilon_o}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \leq \varepsilon_o,$$

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}) - E_{go} = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}) - E_{do(ao)} = E_{do(ao)} \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_o}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

according to the increase in both $E_{gn(gp)}$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)})$,

and for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}) = \frac{\epsilon_o}{\sqrt{1 - \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)}} \geq \epsilon_o$, $\left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 < 1$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}) - E_{go} = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}) - E_{do(ao)} = E_{do(ao)} \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_o}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right], \quad (2)$$

corresponding to the decrease in both $E_{gn(gp)}$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)})$.

Temperature Effect

Here, the intrinsic band gap in the CdS -crystal is found to be given respectively by (Singh & Ravindra, 2012):

$$E_{gin(gip)}(T, r_{d(a)}) = E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}) - \frac{7.092 \times 10^{-4} \times T^2}{T + 94K}. \quad (3)$$

Further, one can define the intrinsic carrier concentration $n_{in(ip)}$ by:

$$n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)}) \equiv N_c(T) \times N_v(T) \times \exp \left(\frac{-E_{gin(gip)}(T, r_{d(a)})}{k_B T} \right), \quad (4)$$

where $N_{c(v)}(T) = 2 \times \left(\frac{m_{c(v)} \times k_B T}{2\pi \hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}$ (cm^{-3}) are the conduction (valence)-band density of states. The numerical results of those energy-band structure parameters are given in the following Table 1.

Table 1. From Equations (1-4) and in the n(p)-type CdS crystal, in which $(m_c/m_o) = 0.197$ and $(m_v/m_o) = 0.801$, the numerical results of the energy-band-structure parameters (He et al., 2022; Kittel, 1976), due to the effect of impurity size are reported, suggesting that, with an increasing $r_{d(a)}$, both $\epsilon(r_{d(a)})$ and $n_{in(ip)}(T = 300 K, r_{d(a)})$ decrease, while the other ones increase.

Donor		S	Se	Te	Sn
r_d (nm)	↗	$r_{do}=0.104$	0.114	0.132	0.140
$\epsilon(r_d)$	↘	$\epsilon_o=9$	8.631	6.809	5.956

$E_d(r_d)$ in meV	↗	$E_{do}=33.13$	36.02	57.88	75.64
$E_{gn}(r_d)$ in eV	↗	$E_{go}=2.582$	2.585	2.607	2.624
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d)$ in eV	↗	$E_{gio}=2.42$	2.423	2.445	2.462
$n_{in}(T = 300K, r_d)$ in $10^{-3}cm^{-3}$	↘	$n_{io}=29.75$	28.14	18.44	13.07
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r_a (nm)	↗	0.126	0.140	0.144	$r_{ao}=0.148$
$\epsilon(r_a)$	↘	9.9685	9.1175	9.1175	$\epsilon_o=9$
$E_a(r_a)$ in meV	↗	109.63	131.06	133.63	$E_{ao}=134.5$
$E_{gp}(r_a)$ in eV	↗	2.557	2.578	2.581	$E_{go}=2.582$
$E_{gip}(T = 300K, r_a)$ in eV	↗	2.395	2.416	2.419	$E_{gio}=2.42$
$n_{ip}(T = 300K, r_a)$ in $10^{-3}cm^{-3}$	↘	48.13	31.80	30.26	$n_{io}=29.75$

Heavy Doping Effect

Here, as given in our previous works (Van Cong and Debais, 1993; Van Cong et al., 2022), the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, band gap narrowing (BGN), and apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), are reported in the following.

First, the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, obtained for any T and any d(a)-density, $N_{d(a)}$, being investigated in our previous paper (Van Cong & Debais, 1993), with a precision of the order of 2.11×10^{-4} is found to be given by:

$$\frac{E_{Fn}(u)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u)}{k_B T} \right) = \frac{G(u) + Au^B F(u)}{1 + Au^B}, \quad A = 0.0005372 \text{ and } B = 4.82842262, \quad (5)$$

where u is the reduced electron density, $u \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{c(v)}}$, $F(u) = au^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 + bu^{-\frac{4}{3}} + cu^{-\frac{8}{3}} \right)^{-\frac{2}{3}}$, $a = \left[(3\sqrt{\pi}/4) \times u \right]^{2/3}$, $b = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\pi}{a} \right)^2$, $c = \frac{62.3739855}{1920} \left(\frac{\pi}{a} \right)^4$, and $G(u) \simeq \ln(u) + 2^{-\frac{3}{2}} \times u \times e^{-du}$; $d = 2^{3/2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}} - \frac{3}{16} \right] > 0$.

Here, one notes that: (i) as $u \gg 1$, according to the HD[d(a)-CdS]ER-case, or to the degenerate case, Eq. (5) is reduced to the function $F(u)$, and (ii) $\frac{E_{Fn}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T} \right) \ll -1$, to the LD[a(d)-CdS]BR-case, or to the non-degenerate case, Eq. (5) is reduced to the function $G(u)$.

Secondly, if denoting the effective Wigner-Seitz radius $r_{sn(sp)}$, characteristic of the interactions, by:

$$r_{sn(sp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) = 1.1723 \times 10^8 \times \left(\frac{g_{c(v)}}{N_{d(a)}} \right)^{1/3} \times \frac{m_{c(v)}}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})},$$

the correlation energy of an effective electron gas, $E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})$, is given as (Van Cong et al., 2022):

$$E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) = \frac{-0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{\left(\frac{2[1-\ln\ln(2)]}{\pi^2}\right) \times \ln(r_{sn(sp)}) - 0.093288}{1+0.03847728 \times r_{sn(sp)}^{1.67378876}}.$$

Now, taking into account various spin-polarized chemical potential-energy contributions such as (Van Cong, 2016): exchange energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, majority-carrier correlation energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, minority hole (electron) correlation energy, majority electron (hole)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, and finally minority hole (electron)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, the band gap narrowing (BGN) are given as follows.

Then, in the n-type heavily doped CdS -crystals, the BGN is found to be given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d) \simeq & a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_d)} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_d)} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cn}(r_{sn}) \times r_{sn}]) + a_3 \times \\ & \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_d)}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_v}{m_c}} \times N_r^{1/4} + a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_d)}} \times N_r^{1/2} \times 2 + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_d)}\right]^2 \times N_r^{1/6}, \\ N_r \equiv & \left(\frac{N_d}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $a_1 = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 6.5 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 5.597 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 8.1 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, and in the p-type heavily doped CdS -crystals, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a) \simeq & a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_a)} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_a)} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cp}(r_{sp}) \times r_{sp}]) + a_3 \times \\ & \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_a)}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_c}{m_v}} \times N_r^{1/4} + 2a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_a)}} \times N_r^{1/2} + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon(r_a)}\right]^2 \times N_r^{1/6}, \\ N_r \equiv & \left(\frac{N_a}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $a_1 = 3.15 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 5.41 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.32 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 4.12 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 9.80 \times 10^{-5}(\text{eV})$.

Therefore, in the HD[d(a)- CdS]ER, we can define the effective extrinsic carrier concentration, $n_{en(ep)}^*$, by :

$$n_{en(ep)}^*(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}) \equiv \sqrt{N_{d(a)} \times p_o(n_o)} = n_{in(ip)} \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}}{2k_B T}\right], \quad (8)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), $\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}$, is defined by:

$$\Delta E_{agn}(N_d, T, r_d) \equiv \Delta E_{gn} + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_d}{N_c}\right) - E_{Fn}(N_d, T),$$

$$\Delta E_{agp}(N_a, T, r_a) \equiv \Delta E_{gp} + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_a}{N_v}\right) + E_{Fp}(N_a, T)]. \quad (9)$$

Total Minority-Carrier Saturation Current Density

In the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdS -junction solar cells, denoted respectively by I(II), the total carrier-minority saturation current density is defined by:

$$J_{oI(oII)} \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)} + J_{Bpo(Bno)} \quad (10)$$

where $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is the minority-electron (hole) saturation current density injected into the LD[a(d)-CdS]BR,

and $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the minority-hole (electron) saturation-current density injected into the HD[d(a)-CdS]ER.

$J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ in the LD[a(d)- CdS]BR

Here, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is determined by (Van Cong, 1999):

$$J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}) = \frac{e \times n_{ip(in)}^2(r_{a(d)}) \times \sqrt{\frac{D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)})}{\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})}}}{N_{a(d)}}, \quad (11)$$

where $n_{ip(in)}^2(r_{a(d)})$ is determined in Table 1, $D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)})$ is the minority electron (minority hole) diffusion coefficient:

$$D_e(N_a, r_a) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[850 + \frac{5750}{1 + \left(\frac{N_a}{8 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{1.8}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_a)}{\varepsilon_0}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}), \quad (12)$$

$$D_h(N_d, r_d) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[85 + \frac{1165}{1 + \left(\frac{N_d}{4 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{0.44}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_d)}{\varepsilon_0}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}), \quad (13)$$

and $\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})$ is the minority electron (minority hole) lifetime in the BR:

$$\tau_{eB}(N_a)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 3 \times 10^{-13} \times N_a + 1.83 \times 10^{-31} \times N_a^2, \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_{hB}(N_d)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 11.76 \times 10^{-13} \times N_d + 2.78 \times 10^{-31} \times N_d^2. \quad (15)$$

$J_{Eno(Epo)}$ in the HD[d(a)- CdS]ER

In the non-uniformly and heavily doped emitter region of d(a)- CdS devices, the effective Gaussian d(a)-density profile or the d(a) (majority-e(h)) density, is defined in such the HD[d(a)- CdS]ER-width W , as (Van Cong et al., 2022):

$$\rho_{d(a)}(x, N_{d(a)}, W) = N_{d(a)} \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x}{W}\right)^2 \times \ln\left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]\right\} \equiv N_{d(a)} \times \left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]^{-\left(\frac{x}{W}\right)^2}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq W,$$

$$N_{do(ao)}(W) \equiv 7.9 \times 10^{17} (2 \times 10^5) \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{W}{184.2 (1) \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}}\right)^{1.066 (0.5)}\right\} (cm^{-3}), \quad (16)$$

where $\rho_{d(a)}(x=0) = N_{d(a)}$ is the surface d(a)-density, and at the emitter-base junction, $\rho_{d(a)}(x=W) = N_{do(ao)}(W)$, which decreases with increasing W . Further, the “effective doping density” is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)}) &\equiv \rho_{d(a)}(x) / \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(\rho_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})}{k_B T}\right], \\ N_{d(a)}^*(x=0, r_{d(a)}) &\equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})}{k_B T}\right]}, \text{ and} \\ N_{d(a)}^*(x=W, r_{d(a)}) &\equiv \frac{N_{do(ao)}(W)}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), r_{d(a)})}{k_B T}\right]}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing $\Delta E_{agn(agg)}$ is determined in Eq. (9), replacing $N_{d(a)}$ by $\rho_{d(a)}(x, N_{d(a)}, W)$. The same remark can be applied to following Equations (18-20).

Now, we can define the minority hole (minority electron) transport parameter $F_{h(e)}$ as:

$$F_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}} = \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}} \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)}} \times \left(\frac{n_{in(ip)}}{n_{in(ip)}^*}\right)^2 \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)} \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}}{k_B T}\right]} (cm^{-5} \times s), \quad (18)$$

the minority hole (electron) diffusion length, $L_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})$ by:

$$L_{h(e)}^{-2}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) = [\tau_{hE(eE)} \times D_{h(e)}]^{-1} = (C \times F_{h(e)})^2 = \left(C \times \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}}\right)^2 = \left(C \times \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}}\right)^2,$$

where the constant C was chosen to be equal to: 2.0893×10^{-30} (cm^4/s), and the minority hole (minority electron) lifetime $\tau_{hE(eE)}$ as:

$$\tau_{hE(eE)} \equiv \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times L_{h(e)}^{-2}} = \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times (C \times F_{e(h)})^2}. \quad (20)$$

Then, under low-level injection, in the absence of external generation, and for the steady-state case, we can define the minority-h(e) density by:

$$p_o(x)[n_o(x)] \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2}{N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)})}, \quad (21)$$

and a normalized excess minority-h(e) density $u(x)$ or a relative deviation between $p(x)[n(x)]$ and $p_o(x)[n_o(x)]$.

$$u(x) \equiv \frac{p(x)[n(x)] - p_o(x)[n_o(x)]}{p_o(x)[n_o(x)]}, \quad (22)$$

which must verify the two following boundary conditions as:

$$u(x=0) \equiv \frac{-J_h(x=0)[J_e(x=0)]}{eS \times p_o(x=0)[n_o(x=0)]},$$

$$u(x=W) = \exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1.$$

Here, $n_{I(I)}(V)$ is a photovoltaic conversion factor determined latter, S ($\frac{cm}{s}$) is the surface recombination velocity at the emitter contact, V is the applied voltage, $V_T \equiv (k_B T/e)$ is the thermal voltage, and the minority-hole (electron) current density $J_{h(e)}(x, r_{d(a)})$.

Further, from the Fick's law for minority hole (electron)-diffusion equations, one has (Van Cong et al., 2022):

$$J_{h(e)}(x, r_{d(a)}) = \frac{-e(+e) \times n_{in(ip)}^2}{F_{h(e)}(x)} \times \frac{du(x)}{dx} = \frac{-e(+e)n_{in(ip)}^2 D_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})}{N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)})} \times \frac{du(x)}{dx}, \quad (23)$$

where $N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)})$ is given in Eq. (17), $D_{h(e)}$ and $F_{h(e)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (12, 13, 18), and from the minority-hole (electron) continuity equation as:

$$\frac{dJ_{h(e)}(x, r_{d(a)})}{dx} = -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(x)}{F_{h(e)}(x) \times L_{h(e)}^2(x)} = -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(x)}{N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)}) \times \tau_{hE(eE)}}, \quad (24)$$

Therefore, the following second-order differential equation is obtained:

$$\frac{d^2u(x)}{dx^2} - \frac{dF_{h(e)}(x)}{dx} \times \frac{du(x)}{dx} - \frac{u(x)}{L_{h(e)}^2(x)} = 0, \quad (25)$$

Then, taking into account the two above boundary conditions given in Eq. (22), one thus gets the general solution of this Eq. (25), as:

$$u(x) = \frac{\sinh(P(x))+I(W,S) \times \cosh(P(x))}{\sinh(P(W))+I(W,S) \times \cosh(P(W))} \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (26)$$

where the factor $I(W, S)$ is determined by:

$$I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)o}(W))}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W))}, \quad (27)$$

Further, since $\frac{dP(x)}{dx} \equiv C \times F_{h(e)}(x) = \frac{1}{L_{h(e)}(x)}$, $C = 2.0893 \times 10^{-30}$ (cm^4/s), for the X-crystal, being an empirical parameter, chosen for each crystalline semiconductor, $P(x)$ is thus found to be defined by:

$$P(x) \equiv \int_0^x \frac{dx}{L_{h(e)}(x)}, \quad 0 \leq x \leq W, \quad P(x = W) \equiv \left(\frac{1}{W} \times \int_0^W \frac{dx}{L_{h(e)}(x)}\right) \times W \equiv \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}^*(x)} = \frac{L_{h(e)}}{L_{h(e)}^*(x)} \times \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}}, \quad (28)$$

where $L_{h(e)}^*(x)$ is the effective minority hole (minority electron) diffusion length. Further, the minority-hole (electron) current density injected into the HD[d(a)- CdS]ER is found to be given by:

$$J_{h(e)}(x, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, V) = -J_{Eno}(x, W, N_d, r_d, S) [J_{Epo}(x, W, N_a, r_a, S)] \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (29)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the saturation minority hole (minority electron) current density,

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(x, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)}) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P(x))+I(W,S) \times \sinh(P(x))}{\sinh(P(W))+I(W,S) \times \cosh(P(W))} \quad (30)$$

In the following, we will denote $P(W)$ and $I(W, S)$ by P and I , for a simplicity. So, Eq. (30) gives:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(x = 0, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(x, r_{d(a)}) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{\sinh(P)+I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (31)$$

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(x = W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(x=W, r_{d(a)}) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (32)$$

and then,

$$\frac{J_{h(e)}(x=0, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, V)}{J_{h(e)}(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, V)} \equiv \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(x=0, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)} = \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (33)$$

Now, if defining the effective excess minority-hole (electron) charge storage in the emitter region by:

$$Q_{h(e)}^*(x = W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) \equiv \int_0^W + e(-e) \times u(x) \times p_o(x) [n_o(x)] \times \frac{\tau_{hE(eE)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)})}{\tau_{hE(eE)}(\rho_{d(a)}(x), r_{d(a)})} dx,$$

and the effective minority hole (minority electron) transit time [$htt(ett)$] by:

$$\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(x = W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S) \equiv Q_{h(e)}^*(x = W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}) / J_{Eno(Epo)}(x = W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S),$$

and from Equations (24, 31), one obtains:

$$\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \equiv 1 - \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(x=0, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)} = 1 - \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (34)$$

Now, some important results can be obtained and discussed below.

As $P \ll 1$ (or $W \ll L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow \infty$, $I \equiv I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W))}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W))} \rightarrow 0$, from Eq. (34), one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 0$, suggesting a completely transparent emitter region (CTER)-case, where, from Eq. (32), one obtains:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(x = W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(x=W, r_{d(a)}) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{P(W)}. \quad (35)$$

Further, as $P \gg 1$ (or $W \gg L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow 0$, $I \equiv I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W))}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W))} \rightarrow \infty$, and from Eq.

(34) one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(x=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 1$, suggesting a completely opaque emitter region (COER)-case, where, from Eq. (32), one gets:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(x = W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(x=W, r_{d(a)}) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \tanh(P). \quad (36)$$

In summary, in the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X-junction solar cells, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{oI(oII)}$, defined in Eq. (10), is now rewritten as:

$$J_{oI(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}) \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S) + J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}), \quad (37)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ and $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (32, 11).

Photovoltaic Conversion Effect at 300K

Here, in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdS -junction solar cells at $T=300$ K, denoted respectively by I(II), and for physical conditions, respectively, as:

$$W = 0.1 \text{ (0.1)} \mu\text{m}, N_{d\equiv s(a\equiv cd)} = 10^{17} \text{ (10}^{17}\text{)} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{do(ao)}, S = 100 \text{ (100)} \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}}\right); N_{a\equiv cd(d\equiv s)} = 10^{16} \text{ (10}^{16}\text{)} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{ao(do)}, \quad (38)$$

we propose, at given open circuit voltages: $V_{ocI1(ocI2)}$ and $V_{ocII1(ocII2)}$, the corresponding data of the short circuit current density $J_{scI(II)}$, in order to formulate our following treatment method of two fix points (Singh & Ravindra, 2012) as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } V_{ocI1(ocI2)} &= V_{ocII1(ocII2)} = 2.041 \text{ (2.076)} \text{ V}, \\ J_{scI1(scI2)} &= J_{scII1(scII2)} = 0.00749 \text{ (0.00939)} \text{ (A/cm}^2\text{)}. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Now, we define the net current density J at $T=300$ K, obtained for the infinite shunt resistance, and expressed as a function of the applied voltage V , flowing through the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdS-junction of solar cells, as:

$$\begin{aligned} J(V) &\equiv J_{ph.}(V) - J_{oI(oII)} \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V)} - 1), \quad X_{I(II)}(V) \equiv \frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}, \\ V_T &\equiv \frac{k_B T}{e} = 0.02585 \text{ V}, \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where the function $n_{I(II)}(V)$ is the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), noting that as $V = V_{oc}$, being the open circuit voltage, $J(V) = 0$, the photocurrent density is defined by: $J_{ph.}(V = V_{oc}) \equiv J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc})$, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$.

Therefore, the photovoltaic conversion effect occurs, according to:

$$J_{scl(sclI)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc}) \equiv J_{ol(olI)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}) \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1), \quad (41)$$

where $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc})$, and $X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{V_{oc}}{n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \times V_T}$.

Here, one remarks that (i) for a given V_{oc} , both $n_{I(II)}$ and $J_{ol(olI)}$ have the same variations, obtained in the same physical conditions, and (ii) the function $(e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1)$ or the PVCF, $n_{I(II)}$, representing the photovoltaic conversion effect, converts the light, represented by $J_{scl(sclI)}$, into the electricity, by $J_{ol(olI)}$.

Then, from Eq. (41), for $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdS -junction solar cells, one respectively obtained:

$n_{I1(I2)}(V_{ocI1(ocI2)}, J_{scl1(sclI2)}) = 1.1022$ (1.1175) and $n_{II1(II2)}(V_{ocII1(ocII2)}, J_{sclII1(sclII2)}) = 1.19919$ (1.21558), noting that, in the work of Singh & Ravindra (2012), their ideal diode factor n was assumed to be 1.

Now, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$, one can propose the general expressions for the PVCF, in order to get exactly the above obtained values of $n_{I1(I2)}$ and $n_{II1(II2)}$, as:

$$n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc}) = n_{I1(I2)} + n_{II1(II2)}, \quad (42)$$

where α (β) = 1.055 (1.0591).

Therefore, one can determine the general expressions for the fill factors, as:

$$F_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V) = \frac{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) - \ln[X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + b]}{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + a}, \quad a, b \geq 0, \quad (43)$$

where a and b will be chosen here, as: $a=1$, $b=0.72$, corresponding to the ideal X-junction solar cells, and $a=b=0$, according to limiting highest values of $F_{I(II)}$.

Finally, the efficiency $\eta_{I(II)}$ can be defined in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ junction solar cells, by:

$$\eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{J_{scl(sclI)} \times V_{oc} \times F_{I(II)}}{P_{in.}}, \quad (44)$$

being assumed to be obtained at 1 sun illumination or at AM1.5G spectrum ($P_{in.} = 0.100 \frac{W}{cm^2}$).

Numerical Results and Concluding Remarks

We will respectively consider the two following cases:

HD [*S*(*Ga*); *Se* (*Mg*); *Te*(*In*); *Sn*(*Cd*)] *CdS* – *ER* –

LD [*Ga* (*S*); *Mg* (*Se*); *In* (*Te*); *Cd* (*Sn*)] *CdS* – *BR* – cases, noting that, for each CdS -crystal, one has: 4 (n^+p) – junctions: ($S^+Ga, Se^+Mg, Te^+In, Sn^+Cd$), and 4 (p^+n) – junctions:

$(Ga^+S, Mg^+Se, In^+Te, Cd^+Sn)$. Then, one now proposes the physical conditions for the determination of various photovoltaic conversion coefficients, as:

$$W = 0.1 \mu m, N_{a(d)} = 10^{17} cm^{-3}, S = 100 (cm/s); N_{a(d)} = 10^{16} cm^{-3}. \quad (45)$$

$n^+ (p^+) - p (n)$ CdS-Junction Solar Cells

First HD [S; Se ; Te; Sn] CdS – ER – LD [Ga ; Mg ; In ; Cd] CdS – BR –case

Here, there are the 4 (n^+p) – CdS junctions, being denoted by: ($S^+Ga, Se^+Mg, Te^+In, Sn^+Cd$).

Then, from the physical conditions given in Eq. (45), one respectively gets: from Eq. (34), $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0, 0)$, suggesting a completely transparent condition, from Eq. (32), $J_{Eno} = (5.27, 4.82, 2.41, 1.35) \times 10^{-38} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$, from Eq. (11), $J_{Bpo} = (1.70, 0.68, 0.61, 0.59) \times 10^{-33} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$, and finally from Eq. (37), $J_{oI} = (1.70, 0.68, 0.61, 0.59) \times 10^{-33} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right) \simeq J_{Bpo}$, which decreases with an increasing r_a , due to the increase in the IBG, as observed in Table 1.

Now, our numerical results of n_I, J_{scl}, F_I , and η_I , are computed, using Equations (42, 41, 43, 44), respectively, and reported in the following Table 2.

Table 2 in Appendix 1.

Second HD [Ga ; Mg ; In ; Cd] CdS – ER – LD [S; Se ; Te; Sn] CdS – BR –case

Here, there are 4 (p^+n) – CdS junctions: ($Ga^+S, Mg^+Se, In^+Te, Cd^+Sn$).

Then, from the physical conditions given in Eq. (45), one respectively obtains: from Eq. (34), $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition, from Eq. (32), $J_{Epo} = (6.10, 2.25, 2.00, 1.92) \times 10^{-31} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$, from Eq. (11), $J_{Bno} = (2.35, 2.01, 0.68, 0.30) \times 10^{-34} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$, and finally from Eq. (37), $J_{oII} = (6.10, 2.25, 2.00, 1.92) \times 10^{-31} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right) \simeq J_{Epo}$, which decreases with an increasing r_a , due to the increase in the IBG, as observed in Table 1.

Now, our numerical results of n_I, J_{scl}, F_I , and η_I , are computed, using Equations (42, 41, 43, 44), respectively, and reported in the following Table 3.

Table 3 in Appendix 1.

In summary, one notes that, with an increasing $r_{a(d)}$:

* $J_{oI(oII)}$ decreases, due to the increase in the IBG, as observed in Table 1, and then

* as observed in Tables 2 and 3, for a given V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), $n_{I(II)}$, decreases, giving rise to the increase in $\eta_{I(II)}$, in good agreement with an important result obtained by Shockley and Queisser (1961), stating that, for a fixed fraction of the total radiative recombination (= 1), and for an increasing IBG [$0 < IBG(eV) \leq 1.1$], η increases and its maximum value is equal to 30 % at IBG=1.1 eV.

Finally, from the well-known Carnot's theorem, obtained from the second principle of the thermodynamics, the maximum efficiency of a heat engine operating between hot (H) and cold (C) reservoirs is the ratio of the temperature difference between the reservoirs to the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , being expressed as:

$$\eta_{max.} = \frac{T_H - T_C}{T_H}, \quad (46)$$

suggesting that $\eta_{max.}$ and T_H have the same variations.

Here, for example, from Tables 2 and 3 for $a=b=0$, as chosen in Eq. (43) for the fill factor F , the values of $\eta_{max.}$ are found to be given by: 43.82 % and 44.05 %, obtained at $V_{oc} = 2.7$ V, and at $T=300$ K $\equiv T_C$. Therefore, from Eq. (46), with $\eta_{max.} = 43.82$ % and 44.05 %, one obtains: $T_H = 534$ K and 536 K, respectively. Thus, as noted above, both $\eta_{max.}$ and T_H increase with an increasing IBG (2.395 eV \leq IBG ≤ 2.462 eV, as seen in Table 1), for such the CdS- crystal at $T=300$ K $\equiv T_C$.

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Appendix 1

Table 2. In the HD[(S; Se; Te; Sn)- CdS] ER-LD[(Ga; Mg; In; Cd)- CdS] BR and for physical conditions given in Eq. (45), our numerical results of n_I , J_{scl} , F_I , and η_I , are computed, using Equations (42, 41, 43, 44), respectively. Here, on notes that, for a given V_{oc} and with increasing $r_{d(a)}$, both J_{ol} and n_I decrease, while other functions J_{scl} , F_I , and η_I increase, being due to the $r_{d(a)}$ -effect, suggesting thus the new obtained results.

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_I	$J_{scl}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	F(%)	$\eta(\%)$
In Eq. (43), obtained for the F as a=1 and b=0.72, according to an ideal solar cells (Green, 1981)				
n^+p	$S^+Ga; Se^+Mg; Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$			
0.041	1.119; 1.104; 1.103; 1.102	7.490; 7.490; 7.490; 7.490	92.64; 92.72; 92.72; 92.73	14.16; 14.17; 14.17; 14.17
2.076	1.134; 1.120; 1.118; 1.117	9.388; 9.415; 9.419; 9.420	92.66; 92.73; 92.74; 92.75	18.06; 18.13; 18.13; 18.14
2.60	1.408; 1.390; 1.388; 1.387	17.64; 17.83; 17.85; 17.86	92.71; 92.78; 92.79; 92.80	42.53; 43.02; 43.08; 43.10
2.70	1.463; 1.444; 1.442; 1.441	17.05; 17.22; 17.24; 17.25	92.71; 92.78; 92.79; 92.79	42.68; 43.15; 43.20; 43.22
2.80	1.518; 1.499; 1.496; 1.495	16.16; 16.31; 16.33; 16.34	92.70; 92.78; 92.79; 92.79	41.96; 42.38; 42.43; 42.45
5.00	2.797; 2.761; 2.757; 2.756	1.802; 1.765; 1.761; 1.760	92.52; 92.60; 92.60; 92.61	8.335; 8.174; 8.155; 8.149
In Eq. (43), obtained for F as a=b=0, according to highest values of F.				
n^+p	$S^+Ga; Se^+Mg; Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$			
0.041	1.119; 1.104; 1.103; 1.102	7.490; 7.490; 7.490; 7.490	93.97; 94.03; 94.03; 94.04	14.36; 14.37; 14.37; 14.37
2.076	1.134; 1.120; 1.118; 1.117	9.388; 9.415; 9.419; 9.420	93.98; 94.04; 94.05; 94.05	18.32; 18.38; 18.39; 18.39
2.60	1.408; 1.390; 1.388; 1.387	17.64; 17.83; 17.85; 17.86	94.02; 94.08; 94.09; 94.09	43.13; 43.62; 43.68; 43.70
2.70	1.463; 1.444; 1.442; 1.441	17.05; 17.22; 17.24; 17.25	94.02; 94.08; 94.09; 94.09	43.29; 43.75; 43.81; 43.82
2.80	1.518; 1.499; 1.496; 1.495	16.16; 16.31; 16.33; 16.34	94.02; 94.08; 94.08; 94.09	42.56; 42.98; 43.03; 43.04
5.00	2.797; 2.761; 2.757; 2.756	1.802; 1.765; 1.761; 1.760	93.87; 93.93; 93.94; 93.94	8.456; 8.292; 8.273; 8.266

Table 3. In the HD[(Ga; Mg; In; Cd)-CdS] ER-LD[(S; Se; Te; Sn)- CdS] BR and for physical conditions given in Eq. (45), our numerical results of n_{II} , J_{sclII} , F_{II} , and η_{II} , are computed, using Equations (42, 41, 43, 44), respectively. Here, on notes that, for a given V_{oc} and with increasing $r_{a(d)}$, both J_{oII} and n_{II} decrease, while other functions J_{sclII} , F_{II} , and η_{II} increase, being due to the $r_{a(d)}$ -effect, suggesting thus the new obtained results.

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scl}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	F(%)	$\eta(\%)$
In Eq. (43), obtained for the F as a=1 and b=0.72, according to an ideal solar cells (Green, 1981).				
p^+n	$Ga^+S; Mg^+Se; In^+Te; Cd^+Sn$			
0.041	1.220; 1.202; 1.200; 1.199	7.490; 7.490; 7.490; 7.490	92.11; 92.21; 92.22; 92.22	14.08; 14.09; 14.10; 14.10
2.076	1.237; 1.218; 1.216; 1.215	9.352; 9.383; 9.387; 9.388	92.13; 92.23; 92.24; 92.24	17.89; 17.97; 17.97; 17.98
2.60	1.534; 1.511; 1.508; 1.507	17.71; 17.93; 17.96; 17.97	92.19; 92.29; 92.30; 92.30	42.45; 43.03; 43.10; 43.13
2.70	1.594; 1.570; 1.567; 1.566	17.17; 17.38; 17.40; 17.41	92.19; 92.28; 92.30; 92.30	42.75; 43.31; 43.37; 43.40
2.80	1.654; 1.629; 1.626; 1.625	16.34; 16.52; 16.54; 16.55	92.19; 92.28; 92.29; 92.29	42.17; 42.68; 42.74; 42.76
5.00	3.054; 3.008; 3.002; 3.000	1.936; 1.892; 1.887; 1.885	91.98; 92.07; 92.09; 92.09	8.904; 8.712; 8.689; 8.682
In Eq. (43), obtained for F as a=b=0, according to highest values of F.				
p^+n	$Ga^+S; Mg^+Se; In^+Te; Cd^+Sn$			
0.041	1.220; 1.202; 1.200; 1.199	7.490; 7.490; 7.490; 7.490	93.55; 93.63; 93.64; 93.64	14.30; 14.31; 14.31; 14.31
2.076	1.237; 1.218; 1.216; 1.215	9.352; 9.383; 9.387; 9.388	93.57; 93.64; 93.65; 93.66	18.17; 18.24; 18.25; 18.25
2.60	1.534; 1.511; 1.508; 1.507	17.71; 17.93; 17.96; 17.97	93.62; 93.69; 93.70; 93.70	43.11; 43.69; 43.76; 43.78
2.70	1.594; 1.570; 1.567; 1.566	17.17; 17.38; 17.40; 17.41	93.61; 93.69; 93.70; 93.70	43.41; 43.97; 44.03; 44.05
2.80	1.654; 1.629; 1.626; 1.625	16.34; 16.52; 16.54; 16.55	93.61; 93.68; 93.69; 93.70	42.82; 43.33; 43.39; 43.41
5.00	3.054; 3.008; 3.002; 3.000	1.936; 1.892; 1.887; 1.885	93.45; 93.52; 93.53; 93.54	9.046; 8.849; 8.826; 8.818